

A CORRELATION STUDY BETWEEN STRESS AND MENTAL HEALTH AMONG PRIMARY TEACHER

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Abstract: *The present research deals with Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher. The samples comprise 60 rural and urban Primary Teacher by using Purposive sampling technique. The tools used for present research are Stress and Mental health Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The data was analyzed using r .*

Findings

There is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of of Primary Teacher.

Keywords: Stress , Mental health

Introduction:

Stress is a normal physical response to events that make you feel threatened or upset your balance in some way. When you sense danger – whether it's real or imagined – the body's defenses kick into high gear in a rapid, automatic process known as the fight-or-flight reaction, or the stress response

Stress at work is a relatively new phenomenon of modern lifestyles. The nature of work has gone through drastic changes over the last century and it is still changing at whirlwind speed. They have touched almost all professions, starting from an artist to a surgeon, or a commercial pilot to a sales executive. With change comes stress will appear automatically. Job stress poses a threat to physical health. Work related stress in the life of organized workers, consequently, affects the health of organizations.

Job stress is a chronic disease caused by conditions in the workplace that negatively affect an individual's performance and overall well-being of his body and mind.

Mental health is more than the mere lack of mental disorders. The positive dimension of mental health is stressed in WHO's definition of health as contained in its constitution: "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." Concepts of mental health include subjective well-being, perceived self-efficacy, autonomy, competence, intergenerational dependence and recognition of the ability to realize one's intellectual and emotional potential. It has also been defined as a state of well-being whereby individuals recognize their abilities, are able to cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively and fruitfully, and make a contribution to their communities.

Hence the investigators selected the topic Correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher.

Statement of the Problem

"A Correlation study between Stress and Mental health among Primary Teacher."

Objective

1. To identify the correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher.
2. To identify the correlation between Stress and Mental health of male Primary Teacher.
3. To identify the correlation between Stress and Mental health of female Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher.
2. There is no significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of male Primary Teacher.

3. There is no significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of female Primary Teacher.

Methodology of the study: Descriptive survey method has been used for the study of the Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher. The sample comprise for the present study is 60 Primary Teacher. Purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data. The following tools were used to collect the data from Primary Teacher. Stress and Mental health Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The obtained data was analyzed by using the Statistical techniques viz. correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation: The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher.

Primary Teacher	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Stress	60	58	.75	.250
	Mental health				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is .250 and the obtain 'r' value is .75 So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

2 There is no significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of male Primary Teacher.

Male Primary Teacher.	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Stress	30	28	0.65	.361
	Mental health				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.65. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of male Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

3 There is no significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of Female Primary Teacher.

Female Primary Teacher.	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Stress	30	28	0.67	.361
	Mental health				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.67. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of female Primary Teacher.

Findings

1. There is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary

Teacher.

2. There is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of female Primary Teacher.

Conclusion

The findings of present study shows that the significant correlation between Stress and Mental health of Primary Teacher. Is observed in case male, female Primary Teacher.

Reference

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